

Research Article

BRIKKA: Building Better with PVC Waste and Epoxy Resin

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Abstract: *Brikka is an innovative stepping stone that serves as an eco-friendly replacement for traditional cement and sand stepping stones. This product is made using recycled materials, particularly PVC conduit, which is difficult to dispose of and contributes to environmental waste. By recycling PVC conduit, we can help reduce waste and support environmental sustainability. One of the key advantages of Brikka is that it is resistant to moss growth, unlike regular stepping stones. Additionally, the product is waterproof, as it is made from waterproof materials, making it more durable and long-lasting. For this project, we used PVC conduit, resin epoxy with hardener epoxy, and a plastic shredder machine to create the product. The drying process takes approximately three days for the product to fully harden and be ready for use. The results of three tests conducted on Brikka showed promising outcomes. The product not only addresses environmental concerns but also helps reduce costs by replacing sand and cement with recycled materials.*

Keywords: Recycled PVC Plastic; resin epoxy; hardener epoxy; plastic shredder.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Brikka is made from recycled PVC plastic and epoxy resin with a durable and versatile product that has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach building material and plastic waste management. By transforming plastic into a usable, custom designed-brick, we're addressing pollution and promoting eco conscious construction at the same time. PVC pipes have undergone significant development over the years, improving their durability and applications in construction (EO Plastic Pipe, n.d.). Additionally, epoxy resins are widely used in various industries due to their strong adhesive properties and chemical resistance (RS Online, n.d.). According to Wikipedia (n.d.), epoxy is a polymer widely used for coatings, adhesives, and composite materials.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

The first step is to crush the PVC conduit using a plastic shredder. Then prepare other materials such as epoxy resin and epoxy hardener. The second step is to mix the hardener and resin in a ratio of 2:1. The third step is pouring the crushed PVC into the mixture. The fourth step is to pour the mixture into the wave shape mold. Finally wait until it turned hard. The time takes to harden completely takes three days.

3. FINDINGS

The compressive strength of bricks made from the PVC and epoxy resins mixture was lower than that of traditional cement bricks but still demonstrated adequate strength for certain construction purposes. PVC mixed with epoxy resins showed better resistance to water absorption compared to cement bricks, indicating improved durability in moist conditions.

In terms of weight, PVC mixed with epoxy resins were noticeably lighter than other bricks like cement bricks, which could ease handling and reduce structural load during construction.

From a cost perspective, the use of waste PVC as raw material significantly reduces production costs for PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks, making them a more economical alternative to cement bricks, which require more expensive raw materials and higher energy input.

4. DISCUSSION

The results show that although traditional cement bricks have higher compressive strength, the PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks offer several significant advantages. First, the PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks are lighter, reducing structural load and making the construction process easier.

Another key advantage is the better water resistance of PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks, making them suitable for damp areas or environments with high moisture risk. This can enhance the lifespan of the bricks and reduce cracking or damage caused by water.

In terms of cost, using waste PVC as raw material makes the production of PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks cheaper compared to other bricks like cement bricks, which require more raw materials and energy. Therefore, besides having good mechanical properties, PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks are also more environmentally friendly and economical choice because they utilize free recycled materials.

Although the compressive strength of PVC mixed with epoxy resins bricks is slightly lower than cement bricks, it is still sufficient for use in low-rise buildings or non-structural walls.

5. CONCLUSION

PVC mixed with epoxy resin bricks offer a new and better option for construction materials. These bricks are stronger and lighter than traditional bricks, making them easier to handle and build with. They also resist water and damage better, which helps buildings last longer. Overall, this innovative material has the potential to make construction more efficient and affordable in the future.

References

EO Plastic Pipe. (n.d.). *PVC pipe development history*. Retrieved from <http://my.eo-plasticpipe.com/info/pvc-pipe-development-history-51444373.html>

RS Online. (n.d.). *Epoxy resin guide*. Retrieved from <https://my.rs-online.com/web/generalDisplay.html?id=ideas-and-advice/epoxy-resin-guide>

Wikipedia. (n.d.). *Epoxy*. Wikipedia. Retrieved May 30, 2025, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Epoxy>